

TOOLS4CAP ACADEMY

MODULE II: ADVANCED DATA MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING FOR CAP STRATEGIC PLANS

20 November 2024

The second **Tools4CAP** (*Innovative Toolbox empowering effective CAP governance towards EU ambitions*) **Academy** module took place on 20 November 2024. The event gathered 65 attendees from different backgrounds. See the agenda [here](#).

Tools4CAP's Academy aims to provide a framework for capacity building and peer-learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme to meet end users' needs. It seeks to promote [meaningful engagement](#) with stakeholders who may benefit from this project. **This second module aimed to:** (i) provide information and examples on advanced data management and monitoring techniques and tools for the CAP Strategic Plans, such as Area Monitoring System, the Policy Monitoring Tool, the Data Aggregation Platform, as well as the Farm Management Information System (FMIS) and the Digital Farm Book, and (ii) develop skills in collecting, processing, and integrating diverse data sources relevant to CAP as well as describe data integration techniques.

During that training session, two presentations were made by [Ecorys](#), as project coordinator, and [AEIDL](#), as Academy coordinator, addressing the following points:

- Presentation of the project, its usefulness for improving the design and monitoring of the national CSPs, and current results.
- Explanation of the objectives, activities, and the upcoming development of the project Academy.

The session included other four presentations on:

- [Tools4CAP work on Integration and interoperability of new data, technology and digitalisation](#), by Daniele Bertolozzi (Ecorys) and Georgios Charvalis (NEUROPUBLIC).
- [New data collecting technologies at farm level \(FMIS\) supporting the design of future CAP intervention](#), provided by Alberto Gutiérrez (ITACyL), and David Sánchez López and Marta Moro Abellán (Spanish Agrarian Guarantee Fund)
- [Agricultural policy information systems for regional performance monitoring](#), by Georgios Charvalis (NEUROPUBLIC).
- [Monitoring systems for CAP Strategic Plans: Area Monitoring System](#), presented by Christian Schingo (ABACO).

The Academy training session, facilitated by Blanca Casares (AEIDL) concluded with a series of next steps including that the meeting materials and the report on the main elements discussed will be available on the [event page](#) and the [YouTube channel](#). This Highlights report will be translated into 16 EU languages covered by the consortium.

ORGANISER:

20 NOVEMBER 2024

ONLINE

65 PARTICIPANTS
(EU institutions; public authorities at national and regional level; researchers; innovators; farmers; and other stakeholders relevant to the agricultural sector)

22 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

If you see this icon, click to see the presentation

If you see this icon, click to see the video

The Tools4CAP project

Daniele Bertolozzi

Tools4CAP project's coordination (Ecorys)

Daniele Bertolozzi (Ecorys) presented the [Tools4CAP](#) project which is a Coordination and Support Action in Horizon Europe (2023-2026) coordinated by [Ecorys](#), gathering 21 [partner organisations](#). It aims to support the design and monitoring of the current national CSPs and lay the foundations for sound preparation of post-2027 Strategic Plans through a bottom-up adaptation of innovative methods and tools.

He began by giving an overview of the main beneficiaries of the project, and continued by explaining the approach to be followed in the upcoming years and the expected main outcomes throughout the project.

Daniele presented the [inventory](#) of methods and tools used in the 27 Member States and introduced the 10 [case studies](#) to be developed in the coming months. She concluded by showcasing the latest key reports available online: (i) [Evaluation of methods and tools](#); (ii) [Assessment of the potential of innovative modelling tools](#); (iii) [Key challenges for decision-making across EU Member States](#); (iv) [Integration of farm level data towards CAP monitoring and evaluation](#); and (v) [Challenges and approaches for landscape monitoring](#).

Tools4CAP beneficiaries

Conceptualisation, evaluation and needs assessment to build a robust **understanding of the New Delivery Model**

Methodological guidelines for the implementation of innovative methods and tools adapted to Member States needs

A Replication Lab to demonstrate the potential of the use of different innovative solutions which can accommodate a diversity of needs through **10 case studies**

An inventory of existing methods and tools used in the design of CAP Strategic Plans of the 27 Member States

A Handbook to support the application of good practices

A Capacity Building Hub to help end users reinforce their capacity to use innovative solutions and good practices

Tools4CAP key outcomes

Introduction to the Tools4CAP Academy

Blanca Casares

Policy expert and project manager (AEIDL)

Blanca Casares (AEIDL) introduced the [Tools4CAP Academy](#), coordinated by [AEIDL](#) in close collaboration with other project partners. The Academy provides a framework for capacity building and peer-learning to develop an attractive and tailored training programme composed of 10 modules to meet the end users' needs.

The Academy aims to:

- Strengthen end user capacity to use innovative methods and tools.
- Facilitate the sharing of results and the exchange of knowledge and best practices.

Tools4CAP Academy modules plan

The results will be consolidated into a Capacity Building Toolkit, which will be translated into 16 EU languages.

In her presentation, Blanca reviewed [Module 1](#), which focused on the project's inventory of methods and tools and was organised on 17 January 2024.

In addition, Blanca explained other activities of the Academy, such as collecting experts' insights through interviews or blog articles, tools factsheets, and joint actions with other projects or networks. She also introduced a dedicated section on the project's website called [Practical Information for CSP](#). It includes relevant documents, from the legal framework, to the approved national CSPs, and key sources for implementation, evaluation and innovation.

The information and materials from the modules will be available in the [specific section](#) of the website, as well as on the event page and [YouTube channel](#).

The project provides the possibility to get involved in different activities: [focus groups](#), [case studies](#), interviews, surveys, training sessions and dissemination efforts. The [consent form](#) is available on the website.

The dedicated section on the project's website called Practical Information for CAP Strategic Plans

Daniele Bertolozzi
Ecorys

Georgios Charvalis
NEUROPUBLIC

Tools4CAP work on integration and interoperability of new data, technology and digitalisation

Daniele Bertolozzi (Ecorys) presented how Tools4CAP is making significant strides in providing Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) decision-makers with suitable tools for a more evidence-based policy making to perform monitoring tasks to review performance of implementation and beneficiaries' compliance. Daniele highlighted the ongoing commitment to supporting the design and monitoring of CSPs, emphasising how the project's outcomes aim to illuminate and provide solutions for the responsibilities assigned to various national bodies involved in the implementation of these plans from 2024–2028. He reviewed the CAP Monitoring regulation framework, stressing how the Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF) has shifted the policy's focus from mere rule compliance to prioritising performance and results, adopting a performance-based delivery model.

He provided an overview of the [inventory](#) of existing methods and tools, which is one of the first results of Tools4CAP. He spoke about the four methodological areas in which methods and tools are classified: (i) Stakeholders needs assessment tools; (ii) Monitoring and data collection tools; (iii) Policy analysis tools for evidence-based decisions, and (iv) Policy choices supporting tools; as well as and how they support the various design and monitoring tasks of CSPs.

Following this, **Georgios Charvalis** (NEUROPUBLIC) underscored the significance of Tools4CAP [work package 4](#) in relation to compliance, performance, and data knowledge. Georgios explained the relationship between different types of data (on-farm and off-farm), technological aspects, and policy aspects in the context of data aggregation and combination.

He concluded his presentation by introducing the project [report](#) (deliverable 4.1) entitled Integration of farm level data towards CAP monitoring and evaluation. It focuses on identifying data sources and monitoring technologies in the agriculture sector, and how they relate to the data needs at the farm level for monitoring and evaluating CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs). Additionally, the project [report](#) (deliverable 4.2), titled Analysis of Challenges and approaches for landscape monitoring, addresses the data gaps that hinder the effective implementation of CSPs. It explores innovative data sources, tools, and mechanisms to support a holistic data collection approach.

Find out more about this in the following news items:

- [Tools4CAP enhances CAP monitoring with new data integration technologies](#)
- [Tools4CAP advances landscape monitoring: Tackling challenges with innovative approaches](#)

Data gaps at different levels of the Strategic Plans

BREAKOUT ROOMS

New data collecting technologies at farm level (FMIS) supporting the design of future CAP intervention

Alberto Gutiérrez

Agricultural Technological Institute of Castilla y Leon - ITACyL

David Sánchez López and Marta Moro Abellán

Spanish Agrarian Guarantee Fund

Alberto Gutiérrez (ITACyL) introduced the [Digital Farm Book \(DFB\) within the context of Tools4CAP](#), known as CUE in Spanish, as a key tool designed to enhance monitoring and data collection capabilities in agricultural practices. It integrates seamlessly into the broader framework of the Tools4CAP initiative, which aims to streamline and improve the efficiency of data-driven decision-making in agriculture, particularly in the context of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Following this introduction, **David Sánchez López** and **Marta Moro Abellán** from the Spanish Agrarian Guarantee Fund presented the regulatory framework for the official DFB in Spain, which is closely linked to the Agrarian Holding Information System (SIEX). SIEX serves as a comprehensive platform that aggregates various agricultural data systems to improve farm management and compliance with regulatory requirements. It encompasses several interconnected elements, including the official Digital Farm Book, ensuring standardisation of data collection across agricultural holdings, enabling better oversight and support for farmers.

SIEX integrates various data streams, including farm inputs, production outputs and environmentally related agricultural practices. The interconnection between these elements facilitates a holistic view of agricultural holdings' performance, enabling more efficient (re)design, monitoring, and reporting. They also emphasised the crucial role of public-private (commercial) collaboration in developing a fully operational system.

Alberto then took the floor again and continued by explaining how the Spanish DFB collects a wide range of information, such as land use, crop types, irrigation practices, and the application of fertilizers and plant protection products. This comprehensive data collection helps track farm performance and adherence to CAP requirements. Alberto remarked that the data collected by the Digital Farm Book is declarative in nature, meaning there is no legal basis for using this data to conduct CAP compliance checks.

Finally, he explained the potential of Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS) as advanced platforms that gather data from various sources, including sensors, satellite imagery, and manual entries. These systems provide capabilities for data analysis, decision support, and reporting, making them invaluable tools for modern agriculture.

Spanish case study workflow within Tools4CAP

The implementation of the Spanish DFB within an FMIS can be illustrated through the example of Plant Protection Products (PPP). By integrating DFB data, an FMIS can track the usage of PPPs, ensuring compliance with safety and environmental regulations while also optimising their application for better crop yields. He concluded by reflecting on how aggregated data from the DFB plays a critical role in evaluating and redesigning CAP Strategic Plans (CSP).

Agricultural policy information systems for regional performance monitoring

Georgios Charvalis

NEUROPUBLIC

Georgios Charvalis (NEUROPUBLIC) presented the case of the new Greek paying agency monitoring system, outlining its key components and its role in enhancing the efficiency of agricultural policy implementation.

He stressed that the new Greek monitoring system is designed to track agricultural activities and land use in member states by leveraging satellite data and digital tools for efficient monitoring. This system is intended to be accurate, transparent, efficient, and timely, ensuring that all data collected and analysed reflects the reality of agricultural practices. Its primary objective is to ensure compliance with the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), particularly in the context of the 2023-2027 implementation. By doing so, the system helps provide financial support to farmers while promoting sustainable agricultural practices across the EU, contributing to broader goals of environmental stewardship and economic stability in the agricultural sector.

The system requires a robust data infrastructure, real-time access to agricultural data, and the ability to integrate multiple monitoring tools. This includes ensuring compatibility with satellite data, farm management systems, and other platforms used for agricultural management. Additionally, the system must comply with EU regulatory standards and provide transparency for farmers and stakeholders.

Georgios explained that recommended practices for setting requirements include using APIs to allow secure data reuse with proper authorisation methods. Open standards should be supported to enable the use of external plug-ins, improving assessments and adding context to parcel declarations. A modular design ensures the tool is reusable, sustainable, and adaptable for future growth. To improve efficiency, interoperability with existing systems like IACS and Sen4CAP, as well as external data sources, should be prioritised. Semantic translation can automate the parsing of data from different systems to ensure compatibility. Additionally, data fusion should combine various datasets to improve accuracy while reducing the need for human intervention.

The case of the new Greek paying agency monitoring stages

He continued by explaining a key component of the system’s design: the incorporation of the Tools4CAP “landscape monitoring framework,” which aims to provide a comprehensive and flexible approach to regional monitoring. This framework enables more localised data analysis and decision-making, allowing tailored interventions based on regional agricultural practices and environmental conditions.

He concluded by presenting two practical examples of regional monitoring tools: (i) the [Policy Monitoring Tool QuantiFarm](#), and (ii) the aggregation dashboard, which allows the real time aggregated data collection from farmers regarding their inputs, practices, crops, etc.

Monitoring systems for CAP Strategic Plans: Area Monitoring System

Christian Schingo

ABACO

Christian Schingo (ABACO) introduced the Area Monitoring System (AMS) as a critical component for monitoring and evaluating agricultural practices within the framework of the Common Agricultural Policy. This system is designed to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of monitoring land use and land cover across agricultural holdings. It plays a key role in ensuring compliance with CAP requirements and providing essential data for policy implementation.

AMS integration in quality assessment process

He presented the regulatory framework for the AMS, which is guided by EU regulations that establish standards for land monitoring, satellite data usage, and compliance verification. These regulations ensure that the AMS aligns with the objectives of the CAP, including environmental

sustainability, agricultural productivity, and fair land management practices. The AMS contributes to (i) the systematic and continuous monitoring of the territory, and (ii) the improvement of the quality of the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) and the Geospatial Aid Application (GSA).

The AMS is a sophisticated tool that leverages satellite imagery and remote sensing technologies to monitor agricultural areas. It can detect changes in land use, crop types, and land cover, providing real-time data to support decision-making processes. By integrating multiple data sources, the system generates accurate and comprehensive maps of agricultural activities.

AMS plays an essential role in verifying the implementation of CAP interventions by providing objective, precise data on land management. It supports the monitoring of compliance with CAP environmental regulations, cross-compliance, and eligibility for direct payments. The system is crucial for enhancing transparency and accountability in agricultural policies. The AMS offers several benefits, including increased efficiency in monitoring agricultural land, improved data accuracy, and reduced administrative burden for both farmers and authorities. By automating the monitoring process, it enables the timely identification of non-compliance issues and promotes more sustainable agricultural practices.

Workflow of satellite monitoring

Christian highlighted that, from a coordination perspective, the AMS operates by integrating satellite data and ground-based information to provide a comprehensive view of agricultural activities. This requires close collaboration between governmental agencies, technology providers, and other stakeholders involved in agricultural policy

implementation. From the farmer's perspective, the AMS offers valuable insights into land use, crop management, and compliance with CAP requirements. Farmers can benefit from the system's ability to identify areas of non-compliance, as well as its role in enhancing farm management through precise monitoring of land activities.

He explained that the satellite monitoring process involves capturing satellite images, which are then processed and analysed to detect changes in land use and agricultural practices. These images are cross-referenced with existing data, allowing for the detection of non-compliance or irregularities in farming practices. He emphasised several key challenges that governance bodies continue to face in utilising AMS within the diverse contexts of CAP Strategic Plans. These challenges include: (i) technological adaptation, (ii) interpretation of data, (iii) dialogue with

farmers, (iv) regional differences, and (v) regulatory adaptation.

Christian concluded by stating that AMS can become a central pillar for the digitalisation and sustainability of agriculture in the EU. Beyond monitoring CAP commitments, it can also promote more resilient and innovative practices in the agricultural sector. However, its effective implementation requires strong political, technical, and economic support.

Participants and speakers from the Academy module on advanced data management and monitoring

In closing the event Blanca Casares (AEIDL) thanked the audience and reminded recordings, presentations and this Highlights report will be available in the coming days on the [event page](#) and the [YouTube channel](#). This highlights report will be soon translated into 16 EU languages covered by the consortium.

All presentations and recordings are available at the [event page](#).

Get involved in the project, [here](#).

Or sign up for the newsletter, [here](#).

New training modules of the Academy will be published in the near future, [here](#).

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